

Neutrosophic *BCC*-ideals in *BCC*-algebras

Sun Shin Ahn

Department of Mathematics Education, Dongguk University, Seoul 04620, Korea

Abstract. The notions of a neutrosophic subalgebra and a neutrosophic ideal of a *BCC*-algebra are introduced and consider characterizations of a neutrosophic subalgebra and a neutrosophic ideal. We define the notion of a neutrosophic *BCC*-ideal of a *BCC*-algebra, and investigated some properties of it.

1. INTRODUCTION

Y. Kormori [8] introduced a notion of a *BCC*-algebras, and W. A. Dudek [4] redefined the notion of *BCC*-algebras by using a dual form of the ordinary definition of Y. Kormori. In [6], J. Hao introduced the notion of ideals in a *BCC*-algebra and studied some related properties. W. A. Dudek and X. Zhang [5] introduced a *BCC*-ideals in a *BCC*-algebra and described connections between such *BCC*-ideals and congruences. S. S. Ahn and S. H. Kwon [2] defined a topological *BCC*-algebra and investigated some properties of it.

Zadeh [10] introduced the degree of membership/truth (*t*) in 1965 and defined the fuzzy set. As a generalization of fuzzy sets, Atanassov [3] introduced the degree of nonmembership/falsehood (*f*) in 1986 and defined the intuitionistic fuzzy set. Smarandache introduced the degree of indeterminacy/neutrality (*i*) as independent component in 1995 (published in 1998) and defined the neutrosophic set on three components (*t, i, f*) = (truth, indeterminacy, falsehood). Jun et. al [7] introduced the notions of a neutrosophic \mathcal{N} -subalgebras and a (closed) neutrosophic \mathcal{N} -ideal in a *BCK/BCI*-algebras and investigated some related properties. subalgebras

In this paper, we introduce the notions of a neutrosophic subalgebra and a neutrosophic ideal of a *BCC*-algebra and consider characterizations of a neutrosophic subalgebra and a neutrosophic ideal. We define the notion of a neutrosophic *BCC*-ideal of a *BCC*-algebra, and investigate some properties of it.

2. PRELIMINARIES

By a *BCC-algebra* [4] we mean an algebra $(X, *, 0)$ of type $(2,0)$ satisfying the following conditions: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (a1) $((x * y) * (z * y)) * (x * z) = 0$,
- (a2) $0 * x = 0$,
- (a3) $x * 0 = x$,
- (a4) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ imply $x = y$.

For brevity, we also call X a *BCC-algebra*. In X , we can define a partial order “ \leq ” by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$. Then \leq is a partial order on X .

⁰ **2010 Mathematics Subject Classification:** 06F35; 03G25; 03B52.

⁰ **Keywords:** *BCC*-algebra; ; (*BCC*-)ideal; neutrosophic subalgebra; neutrosophic (*BCC*-)ideal.

⁰**E-mail:** sunshine@dongguk.edu

Sun Shin Ahn

A *BCC*-algebra X has the following properties: for any $x, y \in X$,

- (b1) $x * x = 0$,
- (b2) $(x * y) * x = 0$,
- (b3) $x \leq y \Rightarrow x * z \leq y * z$ and $z * y \leq z * x$.

Any *BCK*-algebra is a *BCC*-algebra, but there are *BCC*-algebras which are not *BCK*-algebra [4]. Note that a *BCC*-algebra is a *BCK*-algebra if and only if it satisfies:

- (b4) $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Let $(X, *, 0_X)$ and $(Y, *, 0_Y)$ be *BCC*-algebras. A mapping $\varphi : X \rightarrow Y$ is called a *homomorphism* if $\varphi(x *_X y) = \varphi(x) *_Y \varphi(y)$ for all $x, y \in X$. A non-empty subset S of a *BCC*-algebra X is called a *subalgebra* of X if $x * y \in S$ whenever $x, y \in S$. A non-empty subset I of a *BCC*-algebra X is called an *ideal* [6] of X if it satisfies:

- (c1) $0 \in I$,
- (c2) $x * y, y \in I \Rightarrow x \in I$ for all $x, y \in X$.

I is called an *BCC-ideal* [5] of X if it satisfies (c1) and

- (c3) $(x * y) * z, y \in I \Rightarrow x * z \in I$, for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Theorem 2.1. [6] *In a BCC-algebra, an ideal is a subalgebra.*

Theorem 2.2. [5] *In a BCC-algebra, a BCC-ideal is an ideal.*

Corollary 2.3. [5] *Any BCC-ideal of a BCC-algebra is a subalgebra.*

Definition 2.4. Let X be a space of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A simple valued neutrosophic set A in X is characterized by a truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. Then a simple valued neutrosophic set A can be denoted by

$$A := \{ \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \},$$

where $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$ for each point x in X . Therefore the sum of $T_A(x), I_A(x)$, and $F_A(x)$ satisfies the condition $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3$.

For convenience, “simple valued neutrosophic set” is abbreviated to “neutrosophic set” later.

Definition 2.5. Let A be a neutrosophic set in a *B*-algebra X and $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0, 1]$ with $0 \leq \alpha + \beta + \gamma \leq 3$ and an (α, β, γ) -level set of X denoted by $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ is defined as

$$A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} = \{ x \in X \mid T_A(x) \geq \alpha, I_A(x) \leq \beta, F_A(x) \leq \gamma \}.$$

For any family $\{a_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$, we define

$$\bigvee \{a_i \mid i \in \Lambda\} := \begin{cases} \max\{a_i \mid i \in \Lambda\} & \text{if } \Lambda \text{ is finite,} \\ \sup\{a_i \mid i \in \Lambda\} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Neutrosophic *BCC*-ideals in *BCC*-algebras

and

$$\bigwedge \{a_i | i \in \Lambda\} := \begin{cases} \min\{a_i | i \in \Lambda\} & \text{if } \Lambda \text{ is finite,} \\ \inf\{a_i | i \in \Lambda\} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

3. NEUTROSOPHIC *BCC*-IDEALS

In what follows, let X be a *BCC*-algebra unless otherwise specified.

Definition 3.1. A neutrosophic set A in a *BCC*-algebra X is called a *neutrosophic subalgebra* of X if it satisfies:

$$(NSS) \quad T_A(x * y) \leq \max\{T_A(x), T_A(y)\}, I_A(x * y) \geq \min\{I_A(x), I_A(y)\}, \text{ and } F_A(x * y) \leq \max\{F_A(x), F_A(y)\}, \text{ for any } x, y \in X.$$

Proposition 3.2. Every neutrosophic subalgebra of a *BCC*-algebra X satisfies the following conditions:

$$(3.1) \quad T_A(0) \leq T_A(x), I_A(0) \geq I_A(x), \text{ and } F_A(0) \leq F_A(x) \text{ for any } x \in X.$$

Proof. Straightforward. □

Example 3.3. Let $X := \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a *BCC*-algebra [6] with the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1
2	2	1	0	1
3	3	3	3	0

Define a neutrosophic set A in X as follows:

$$T_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.12 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1, 2\} \\ 0.83 & \text{if } x = 3, \end{cases}$$

$$I_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.81 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1, 2\} \\ 0.14 & \text{if } x = 3, \end{cases}$$

and

$$F_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.12 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1, 2\} \\ 0.83 & \text{if } x = 3. \end{cases}$$

It is easy to check that A is a neutrosophic subalgebra of X .

Theorem 3.4. Let A be a neutrosophic set in a *BCC*-algebra X and let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0, 1]$ with $0 \leq \alpha + \beta + \gamma \leq 3$. Then A is a neutrosophic subalgebra of X if and only if all of (α, β, γ) -level set $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ are subalgebras of X when $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. Assume that A is a neutrosophic subalgebra of X . Let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0, 1]$ be such that $0 \leq \alpha + \beta + \gamma \leq 3$ and $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} \neq \emptyset$. Let $x, y \in A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$. Then $T_A(x) \leq \alpha, T_A(y) \leq \alpha, I_A(x) \geq \beta, I_A(y) \geq \beta$ and $F_A(x) \leq \gamma, F_A(y) \leq \gamma$. Using (NSS), we have $T_A(x * y) \leq \max\{T_A(x), T_A(y)\} \leq \alpha, I_A(x * y) \geq \min\{I_A(x), I_A(y)\} \geq \beta$, and $F_A(x * y) \leq \max\{F_A(x), F_A(y)\} \leq \gamma$. Hence $x * y \in A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$. Therefore $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ is a subalgebra of X .

Conversely, all of (α, β, γ) -level set $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ are subalgebras of X when $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} \neq \emptyset$. Assume that there exist $a_t, b_t, a_i, b_i \in X$ and $a_f, b_f \in X$ such that $T_A(a_t * b_t) > \max\{T_A(a_t), T_A(b_t)\}, I_A(a_i * b_i) < \min\{I_A(a_i), I_A(b_i)\}$

Sun Shin Ahn

and $F_A(a_f * b_f) > \max\{F_A(a_f), F_A(b_f)\}$. Then $T_A(a_t * b_t) > \alpha_1 \geq \max\{T_A(a_t), T_A(b_t)\}$, $I_A(a_i * b_i) < \beta_1 \leq \min\{I_A(a_i), I_A(b_i)\}$ and $F_A(a_f * b_f) > \gamma_1 \geq \max\{F_A(a_f), F_A(b_f)\}$ for some $\alpha_1, \gamma_1 \in [0, 1)$ and $\beta_1 \in (0, 1]$. Hence $a_t, b_t, a_i, b_i \in A^{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1)}$, and $a_f, b_f \in A^{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1)}$. But $a_t * b_t, a_i * b_i \notin A^{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1)}$, and $a_f * b_f \notin A^{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1)}$, which is a contradiction. Hence $T_A(x * y) \leq \max\{T_A(x), T_A(y)\}$, $I_A(x * y) \geq \min\{I_A(x), I_A(y)\}$, and $F_A(x * y) \leq \max\{F_A(x), F_A(y)\}$, for any $x, y \in X$. Therefore A is a neutrosophic subalgebra of X . \square

Since $[0, 1]$ is a completely distributive lattice with respect to the usual ordering, we have the following theorem.

Theorem 3.5. *If $\{A_i | i \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is a family of neutrosophic subalgebras of a BCC-algebra X , then $(\{A_i | i \in \mathbb{N}\}, \subseteq)$ forms a complete distributive lattice.*

Theorem 3.6. *Let A be a neutrosophic subalgebra of a BCC-algebra X . If there exists a sequence $\{a_n\}$ in X such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} T_A(a_n) = 0$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_A(a_n) = 1$, and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} F_A(a_n) = 0$, then $T_A(0) = 0$, $I_A(0) = 1$, and $F_A(0) = 0$.*

Proof. By Proposition 3.2, we have $T_A(0) \leq T_A(x)$, $I_A(0) \geq I_A(x)$, and $F_A(0) \leq F_A(x)$ for all $x \in X$. Hence we have $T_A(0) \leq T_A(a_n)$, $I_A(0) \geq I_A(a_n)$, and $F_A(0) \leq F_A(a_n)$ for every positive integer n . Therefore $0 \leq T_A(0) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} T_A(a_n) = 0$, $1 = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_A(a_n) \leq I_A(0) \leq 1$, and $0 \leq F_A(0) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} F_A(a_n) = 0$. Thus we have $T_A(0) = 0$, $I_A(0) = 1$, and $F_A(0) = 0$. \square

Proposition 3.7. *If every neutrosophic subalgebra A of a BCC-algebra X satisfies the condition*

$$(3.2) \quad T_A(x * y) \leq T_A(y), I_A(x * y) \geq I_A(y), F_A(x * y) \leq F_A(y), \text{ for any } x, y \in X,$$

then T_A, I_A , and F_A are constant functions.

Proof. It follows from (3.2) that $T_A(x) = T_A(x * 0) \leq T_A(0)$, $I_A(x) = I_A(x * 0) \geq I_A(0)$, and $F_A(x) = F_A(x * 0) \leq F_A(0)$ for any $x \in X$. By Proposition 3.2, we have $T_A(x) = T_A(0)$, $I_A(x) = I_A(0)$, and $F_A(x) = F_A(0)$ for any $x \in X$. Hence T_A, I_A , and F_A are constant functions. \square

Theorem 3.8. *Every subalgebra of a BCC-algebra X can be represented as an (α, β, γ) -level set of a neutrosophic subalgebra A of X .*

Proof. Let S be a subalgebra of a BCC-algebra X and let A be a neutrosophic subalgebra of X . Define a neutrosophic set A in X as follows:

$$T_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad x \mapsto \begin{cases} \alpha_1 & \text{if } x \in S \\ \alpha_2 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$$I_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad x \mapsto \begin{cases} \beta_1 & \text{if } x \in S \\ \beta_2 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$$F_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad x \mapsto \begin{cases} \gamma_1 & \text{if } x \in S \\ \gamma_2 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

where $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in [0, 1)$ and $\beta_1, \beta_2 \in (0, 1]$ with $\alpha_1 < \alpha_2, \beta_1 > \beta_2, \gamma_1 < \gamma_2$, and $0 \leq \alpha_1 + \beta_1 + \gamma_1 \leq 3, 0 \leq \alpha_2 + \beta_2 + \gamma_2 \leq 3$. Obviously, $S = A^{(\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1)}$. We now prove that A is a neutrosophic subalgebra of X . Let $x, y \in X$. If $x, y \in S$, then $x * y \in S$ because S is a subalgebra of X . Hence $T_A(x) = T_A(y) = T_A(x * y) = \alpha_1$,

Neutrosophic *BCC*-ideals in *BCC*-algebras

$I_A(x) = I_A(y) = I_A(x * y) = \beta_1$, $F_A(x) = F_A(y) = F_A(x * y) = \gamma_1$ and so $T_A(x * y) \leq \max\{T_A(x), T_A(y)\}$, $I_A(x * y) \geq \min\{I_A(x), I_A(y)\}$, $F_A(x * y) \leq \max\{F_A(x), F_A(y)\}$. If $x \in S$ and $y \notin S$, then $T_A(x) = \alpha_1, T_A(y) = \alpha_2$, $I_A(x) = \beta_1, I_A(y) = \beta_2$, $F_A(x) = \gamma_1, F_A(y) = \gamma_2$ and so $T_A(x * y) \leq \max\{T_A(x), T_A(y)\} = \alpha_2$, $I_A(x * y) \geq \min\{I_A(x), I_A(y)\} = \beta_2$, $F_A(x * y) \leq \max\{F_A(x), F_A(y)\} = \gamma_2$. Obviously, if $x \notin A$ and $y \notin A$, then $T_A(x * y) \leq \max\{T_A(x), T_A(y)\} = \alpha_2$, $I_A(x * y) \geq \min\{I_A(x), I_A(y)\} = \beta_2$, $F_A(x * y) \leq \max\{F_A(x), F_A(y)\} = \gamma_2$. Therefore A is a neutrosophic subalgebra of X . \square

Definition 3.9. A neutrosophic set A in a *BCC*-algebra X is said to be *neutrosophic ideal* of X if it satisfies:

(NSI1) $T_A(0) \leq T_A(x), I_A(0) \geq I_A(x)$, and $F_A(0) \leq F_A(x)$ for any $x \in X$;

(NSI2) $T_A(x) \leq \max\{T_A(x * y), T_A(y)\}, I_A(x) \geq \min\{I_A(x * y), I_A(y)\}$, and $F_A(x) \leq \max\{F_A(x * y), F_A(y)\}$, for any $x, y \in X$.

Proposition 3.10. Every neutrosophic ideal of a *BCC*-algebra X is a neutrosophic subalgebra of X .

Proof. Let A be a neutrosophic ideal of X . Put $x := x * y$ and $y := x$ in (NSI2). Then we have $T_A(x * y) \leq \max\{T_A((x * y) * x), T_A(x)\}, I_A(x * y) \geq \min\{I_A((x * y) * x), I_A(x)\}$, and $F_A(x * y) \leq \max\{F_A((x * y) * x), F_A(x)\}$. It follows from (b2) and (NSI1) that $T_A(x * y) \leq \max\{T_A((x * y) * x), T_A(x)\} = \max\{T_A(0), T_A(x)\} \leq \max\{T_A(x), T_A(y)\}, I_A(x * y) \geq \min\{I_A((x * y) * x), I_A(x)\} = \max\{I_A(0), I_A(x)\} \geq \max\{I_A(x), I_A(y)\}$, and $F_A(x * y) \leq \max\{F_A((x * y) * x), F_A(x)\} = \max\{F_A(0), F_A(x)\} \leq \max\{F_A(x), F_A(y)\}$. Thus A is a neutrosophic subalgebra of X . \square

Theorem 3.11. Let A be a neutrosophic set in a *BCC*-algebra X and let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0, 1]$ with $0 \leq \alpha + \beta + \gamma \leq 3$. Then A is a neutrosophic ideal of X if and only if all of (α, β, γ) -level set $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ are ideals of X when $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. Assume that A is a neutrosophic ideal of X . Let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0, 1]$ be such that $0 \leq \alpha + \beta + \gamma \leq 3$ and $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} \neq \emptyset$. Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x * y, y \in A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$. Then $T_A(x * y) \leq \alpha, T_A(y) \leq \alpha, I_A(x * y) \geq \beta, I_A(y) \geq \beta$, and $F_A(x * y) \leq \gamma, F_A(y) \leq \gamma$. By Definition 3.9, we have $T_A(0) \leq T_A(x) \leq \max\{T_A(x * y), T_A(y)\} \leq \alpha, I_A(0) \geq I_A(x) \geq \min\{I_A(x * y), I_A(y)\} \geq \beta$, and $F_A(0) \leq F_A(x) \leq \max\{F_A(x * y), T_A(y)\} \leq \gamma$. Hence $0, x \in A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$. Therefore $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ is an ideal of X .

Conversely, suppose that there exist $a, b, c \in X$ such that $T_A(0) > T_A(a), I_A(0) < I_A(b)$, and $F_A(0) > F_A(c)$. Then there exist $a_t, c_t \in [0, 1]$ and $b_t \in (0, 1]$ such that $T_A(0) > a_t \geq T_A(a), I_A(0) < b_t \leq I_A(b)$ and $F_A(0) > c_t \geq F_A(c)$. Hence $0 \notin A^{(a_t, b_t, c_t)}$, which is a contradiction. Therefore $T_A(0) \leq T_A(x), I_A(0) \geq I_A(x)$ and $F_A(0) \leq F_A(x)$ for all $x \in X$. Assume that there exist $a_t, b_t, a_i, b_i, a_f, b_f \in X$ such that $T_A(a_t) > \max\{T_A(a_t * b_t), T_A(b_t)\}, I_A(a_i) < \min\{I_A(a_i * b_i), I_A(b_i)\}$, and $F_A(a_f) > \max\{T_A(a_f * b_f), T_A(b_f)\}$. Then there exist $s_t, s_f \in [0, 1]$ and $s_i \in (0, 1]$ such that $T_A(a_t) > s_t \geq \max\{T_A(a_t * b_t), T_A(b_t)\}, I_A(a_i) < s_i \leq \min\{I_A(a_i * b_i), I_A(b_i)\}$, and $F_A(a_f) > s_f \geq \max\{T_A(a_f * b_f), T_A(b_f)\}$. Hence $a_t * b_t, b_t, a_i * b_i, a_f * b_f \in A^{(s_t, s_i, s_f)}$, and $b_t, b_i, b_f \in A^{(s_t, s_i, s_f)}$. But $a_t, a_i \notin A^{(s_t, s_i, s_f)}$ and $a_f \notin A^{(s_t, s_i, s_f)}$. This is a contradiction. Therefore $T_A(x) \leq \max\{T_A(x * y), T_A(y)\}, I_A(x) \geq \min\{I_A(x * y), I_A(y)\}$ and $F_A(x) \leq \max\{F_A(x * y), F_A(y)\}$, for any $x, y \in X$. Therefore A is a neutrosophic ideal of X . \square

Proposition 3.12. Every neutrosophic ideal A of a *BCC*-algebra X satisfies the following properties:

Sun Shin Ahn

- (i) $(\forall x, y \in X)(x \leq y \Rightarrow T_A(x) \leq T_A(y), I_A(x) \geq I_A(y), F_A(x) \leq F_A(y)),$
- (ii) $(\forall x, y, z \in X)(x * y \leq z \Rightarrow T_A(x) \leq \max\{T_A(y), T_A(z)\}, I_A(x) \geq \min\{I_A(y), I_A(z)\}, F_A(x) \leq \max\{F_A(y), F_A(z)\}).$

Proof. (i) Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x \leq y$. Then $x * y = 0$. Using (NSI2) and (NSI1), we have $T_A(x) \leq \max\{T_A(x * y), T_A(y)\} = \max\{T_A(0), T_A(y)\} = T_A(y), I_A(x) \geq \min\{I_A(x * y), I_A(y)\} = \min\{I_A(0), I_A(y)\} = I_A(y)$, and $F_A(x) \leq \max\{F_A(x * y), F_A(y)\} = \max\{F_A(0), F_A(y)\} = F_A(y)$.

(ii) Let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $x * y \leq z$. By (NSI2) and (NSI1). we get $T_A(x * y) \leq \max\{T_A((x * y) * z), T_A(z)\} = \max\{T_A(0), T_A(z)\} = T_A(z), I_A(x * y) \geq \min\{I_A((x * y) * z), I_A(z)\} = \min\{I_A(0), I_A(z)\} = I_A(z)$, and $F_A(x * y) \leq \max\{F_A((x * y) * z), F_A(z)\} = \max\{F_A(0), F_A(z)\} = F_A(z)$. Hence $T_A(x) \leq \max\{T_A(x * y), T_A(y)\} \leq \max\{T_A(y), T_A(z)\}, I_A(x) \geq \min\{I_A(x * y), I_A(y)\} \geq \min\{I_A(y), I_A(z)\}$, and $F_A(x) \leq \max\{F_A(x * y), F_A(y)\} \leq \max\{F_A(y), F_A(z)\}$. □

The following corollary is easily proved by induction.

Corollary 3.13. *Every neutrosophic ideal A of a BCC-algebra X satisfies the following property:*

$$(3.3) \quad (\cdots (x * a_1) * \cdots) * a_n = 0 \Rightarrow T_A(x) \leq \bigvee_{k=1}^n T_A(a_k), I_A(x) \geq \bigwedge_{k=1}^n I_A(a_k), F_A(x) \leq \bigvee_{k=1}^n F_A(a_k), \text{ for all } x, a_1, \dots, a_n \in X.$$

Definition 3.14. Let A and B be neutrosophic sets of a set X . The *union* of A and B is defined to be a neutrosophic set

$$A \tilde{\cup} B := \{ \langle x, T_{A \cup B}(x), I_{A \cup B}(x), F_{A \cup B}(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \},$$

where $T_{A \cup B}(x) = \min\{T_A(x), T_B(x)\}, I_{A \cup B}(x) = \max\{I_A(x), I_B(x)\}, F_{A \cup B}(x) = \min\{F_A(x), F_B(x)\}$, for all $x \in X$. The *intersection* of A and B is defined to be a neutrosophic set

$$A \tilde{\cap} B := \{ \langle x, T_{A \cap B}(x), I_{A \cap B}(x), F_{A \cap B}(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \},$$

where $T_{A \cap B}(x) = \max\{T_A(x), T_B(x)\}, I_{A \cap B}(x) = \min\{I_A(x), I_B(x)\}, F_{A \cap B}(x) = \max\{F_A(x), F_B(x)\}$, for all $x \in X$.

Theorem 3.15. *The intersection of two neutrosophic ideals of a BCC-algebra X is also a neutrosophic ideal of X .*

Proof. Let A and B be neutrosophic ideals of X . For any $x \in X$, we have $T_{A \cap B}(0) = \max\{T_A(0), T_B(0)\} \leq \max\{T_A(x), T_B(x)\} = T_{A \cap B}(x), I_{A \cap B}(0) = \min\{I_A(0), I_B(0)\} \geq \min\{I_A(x), I_B(x)\} = I_{A \cap B}(x)$, and $F_{A \cap B}(0) = \max\{F_A(0), F_B(0)\} \leq \max\{F_A(x), F_B(x)\} = F_{A \cap B}(x)$. Let $x, y \in X$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_{A \cap B}(x) &= \max\{T_A(x), T_B(x)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\max\{T_A(x * y), T_A(y)\}, \max\{T_B(x * y), T_B(y)\}\} \\ &= \max\{\max\{T_A(x * y), T_B(x * y)\}, \max\{T_A(y), T_B(y)\}\} \\ &= \max\{T_{A \cap B}(x * y), T_{A \cap B}(y)\}, \end{aligned}$$

Neutrosophic *BCC*-ideals in *BCC*-algebras

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{A \cap B}(x) &= \min\{I_A(x), I_B(x)\} \\
 &\geq \min\{\min\{I_A(x * y), I_A(y)\}, \min\{I_B(x * y), I_B(y)\}\} \\
 &= \min\{\min\{I_A(x * y), I_B(x * y)\}, \min\{I_A(y), I_B(y)\}\} \\
 &= \min\{I_{A \cap B}(x * y), I_{A \cap B}(y)\},
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{A \cap B}(x) &= \max\{F_A(x), F_B(x)\} \\
 &\leq \max\{\max\{F_A(x * y), F_A(y)\}, \max\{F_B(x * y), F_B(y)\}\} \\
 &= \max\{\max\{F_A(x * y), F_B(x * y)\}, \max\{F_A(y), F_B(y)\}\} \\
 &= \max\{F_{A \cap B}(x * y), F_{A \cap B}(y)\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence $A \tilde{\cap} B$ is a neutrosophic ideal of X . □

Corollary 3.16. *If $\{A_i | i \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is a family of neutrosophic ideals of a *BCC*-algebra X , then so is $\tilde{\cap}_{i \in \mathbb{N}} A_i$.*

The union of any set of neutrosophic ideals of a *BCC*-algebra X need not be a neutrosophic ideal of X .

Example 3.17. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ be a *BCC*-algebra [5] with the following table:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0	0
2	2	2	0	0	0
3	3	3	1	0	0
4	4	3	4	3	0

Define neutrosophic sets A and B of X as follows:

$$T_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.12, & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1\} \\ 0.74 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$$I_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.63, & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1\} \\ 0.11 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$$F_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.12, & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1\} \\ 0.74 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$$T_B : X \rightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.13, & \text{if } x \in \{0, 2\} \\ 0.63 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

$$I_B : X \rightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.75, & \text{if } x \in \{0, 2\} \\ 0.14 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

and

$$F_B : X \rightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.13, & \text{if } x \in \{0, 2\} \\ 0.63 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

It is easy to check that A and B are neutrosophic ideals of X . But $A \tilde{\cup} B$ is not a neutrosophic ideal of X , since $T_{A \tilde{\cup} B}(3) = \min\{T_A(3), T_B(3)\} = 0.63 \not\leq \max\{T_{A \tilde{\cup} B}(3 * 2), T_{A \tilde{\cup} B}(2)\} = \max\{T_{A \tilde{\cup} B}(1), T_{A \tilde{\cup} B}(2)\} = \max\{\min\{T_A(1), T_B(1)\}, \min\{T_A(2), T_B(2)\}\} = \max\{0.12, 0.13\} = 0.13$.

Sun Shin Ahn

Definition 3.18. A neutrosophic set A in a BCC -algebra X is said to be a *neutrosophic BCC -ideal* of X if it satisfies (NSI1) and

$$(NSI3) \quad T_A(x * z) \leq \max\{T_A((x * y) * z), T_A(y)\}, I_A(x * z) \geq \min\{I_A((x * y) * z), I_A(y)\}, \text{ and } F_A(x * z) \leq \max\{F_A((x * y) * z), F_A(y)\}, \text{ for any } x, y, z \in X.$$

Lemma 3.19. Every neutrosophic BCC -ideal of a BCC -algebra X is a neutrosophic ideal of X .

Proof. Let A be a neutrosophic BCC -ideal of a BCC -algebra X . Put $z := 0$ in (NSI3). By (a3), we have $T_A(x * 0) = T_A(x) \leq \max\{T_A((x * y) * 0), T_A(y)\} = \max\{T_A(x * y), T_A(y)\}$, $I_A(x * 0) = I_A(x) \geq \min\{I_A((x * y) * 0), I_A(y)\} = \min\{I_A(x * y), I_A(y)\}$, and $F_A(x * 0) = F_A(x) \leq \max\{F_A((x * y) * 0), F_A(y)\} = \max\{F_A(x * y), F_A(y)\}$, for any $x, y \in X$. Hence A is a neutrosophic ideal of X . \square

Corollary 3.20. Every neutrosophic BCC -ideal of a BCC -algebra X is a neutrosophic subalgebra of X .

The converse of Proposition 3.10 and Lemma 3.19 need not be true in general (see Example 3.21).

Example 3.21. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ be a BCC -algebra as in Example 3.17. Define a neutrosophic set A of X as follows:

$$T_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.13 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\} \\ 0.83 & \text{if } x = 4, \end{cases}$$

$$I_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.82 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\} \\ 0.11 & \text{if } x = 4, \end{cases}$$

and

$$F_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.13 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\} \\ 0.83 & \text{if } x = 4, \end{cases}$$

It is easy to check that A is a neutrosophic subalgebra of X , but not a neutrosophic ideal of X , since $T_A(4) = 0.83 \not\leq \max\{T_A(4 * 3), T_A(3)\} = \max\{T_A(3), T_A(3)\} = 0.13$. Consider a neutrosophic set B of X which is given by

$$T_B : X \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.14 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1\}, \\ 0.84 & \text{if } x \in \{2, 3, 4\} \end{cases}$$

$$I_B : X \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.85 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1\} \\ 0.12 & \text{if } x \in \{2, 3, 4\}, \end{cases}$$

and

$$F_B : X \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.14 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1\} \\ 0.84 & \text{if } x \in \{2, 3, 4\}. \end{cases}$$

It is easy to show that B is a neutrosophic ideal of X , but not a neutrosophic BCC -ideal of X , since $T_B(4 * 3) = T_B(3) = 0.84 \not\leq \max\{T_B((4 * 1) * 3), T_B(1)\} = \max\{T_B(0), T_B(1)\} = 0.14$.

Neutrosophic *BCC*-ideals in *BCC*-algebras

Example 3.22. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ be a *BCC*-algebra [5] with the following table:

*	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0	1
2	2	2	0	0	1	1
3	3	2	1	0	1	1
4	4	4	4	4	0	1
5	5	5	5	5	5	0

Define a neutrosophic set A of X as follows:

$$T_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.43 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\} \\ 0.55 & \text{if } x = 5, \end{cases}$$

$$I_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.54 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\} \\ 0.42 & \text{if } x = 5, \end{cases}$$

and

$$F_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], x \mapsto \begin{cases} 0.43 & \text{if } x \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\} \\ 0.55 & \text{if } x = 5. \end{cases}$$

It is easy to check that A is a neutrosophic *BCC*-ideal of X .

Theorem 3.23. Let A be a neutrosophic set in a *BCC*-algebra X and let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0, 1]$ with $0 \leq \alpha + \beta + \gamma \leq 3$. Then A is a neutrosophic *BCC*-ideal of X if and only if all of (α, β, γ) -level set $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)}$ are *BCC*-ideals of X when $A^{(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)} \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. Similar to Theorem 3.11. □

Proposition 3.24. Let A be a neutrosophic *BCC*-ideal of a *BCC*-algebra X . Then $X_T := \{x \in X | T_A(x) = T_A(0)\}$, $X_I := \{x \in X | I_A(x) = I_A(0)\}$, and $X_F := \{x \in X | F_A(x) = F_A(0)\}$ are *BCC*-ideals of X .

Proof. Clearly, $0 \in X_T$. Let $(x * y) * z, y \in X_T$. Then $T_A((x * y) * z) = T_A(0)$ and $T_A(y) = T_A(0)$. It follows from (NSI3) that $T_A(x * z) \leq \max\{T_A((x * y) * z), T_A(y)\} = T_A(0)$. By (NSI1), we get $T_A(x * z) = T_A(0)$. Hence $x * z \in X_T$. Therefore X_T is a *BCC*-ideal of X . By a similar way, X_I and X_F are *BCC*-ideals of X . □

REFERENCES

[1] S. S. Ahn, Applications of soft sets to *BCC*-ideals in *BCC*-algebras, J. Comput. Anal. Appl. (to appear).
 [2] S. S. Ahn and S. H. Kwon, Topological properties in *BCC*-algebras, Commun. Korean Math. Soc. **23(2)** (2008), 169-178.
 [3] K. Atanassov, *Intuitionistic fuzzy sets*, Fuzzy sets and Systems 20 (1986), 87–96.
 [4] W. A. Dudek, *On constructions of BCC-algebras*, Selected Papers on *BCK*- and *BCI*-algebras **1** (1992), 93-96.
 [5] W. A. Dudek and X. Zhang, *On ideals and congruences in BCC-algebras*, Czecho Math. J. **48** (1998), 21-29.
 [6] J. Hao, *Ideal Theory of BCC-algebras*, Sci. Math. Japo. **3** (1998), 373-381.
 [7] Y. B. Jun, F. Smarandache and H. Bordbar, *Neutrosophic \mathcal{N} -structures applied to BCK/BCI-algebras*, Information, (to submit).
 [8] Y. Kormori, *The class of BCC-algebras is not a variety*, Math. Japo. **29** (1984), 391-394.

Sun Shin Ahn

- [9] F. Smarandache, Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Probability, Sets, and Logic, Amer. Res. Press, Rehoboth, USA, 1998.
- [10] L. A. Zadeh, Fuzzy sets, Inform. Control **8** (1965), 338-353.